

Ethanol Yield of Three Varieties of Cassava (“Odongbo”, “Ofege” and TMS 30572) using α -amylase from Germinated Paddy Rice and Yeast from Palm Wine

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Abstract : A process of conversion of flour from three varieties of cassava, namely Odongbo, ofege and TMS30752 to ethanol using α -amylase locally sourced from germinated unhusked paddy rice and yeast isolated from palm wine was developed. It involves the germination of paddy rice for a period of 15days to produce α -amylase for starch hydrolysis and isolation of yeast from palm wine for fermentation. The results showed that optimum amylase yield of “ofada” rice paddy was at 6th day germination which was 576.9ml/g. Ethanol yield for TMS30572 (440.3%) was significantly higher than “Odongbo” (160.2%) and “Ofege” (115.1%), Sugar conversion efficiency were 311.0%v/v, 268.2%v/v and 186.84%v/v for TMS30572, “Odongbo” and “Ofege” respectively. The ethanol boiling points were 78oC, 76oC and 80oC for TMS30572, “Odongbo” and “Ofege” respectively. This study showed that cassava varieties affects quality of ethanol produced and germination of “ofada” rice for 6 days ensures optimum production of crude amylase enzyme.

Keywords : cassava, ethanol, fermentation, hydrolysis, α -amylase.

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